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ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1493-6630>**On the nature of strong interactions****Annotation**

The existing concept of the nature of nuclear forces has a number of disadvantages. The article proves that these forces can be substantiated as a consequence of Maxwell's equations. In this case, it is assumed that the nucleons rotate around their own axis with a certain angular velocity ω . It is shown that the detected repulsive forces exceed the Coulomb forces of attraction by a factor of ω . It is shown that, in spite of mutual attraction, rotating nucleons cannot touch.

Contents

1. Introduction \
2. Interaction of moving electric charges \
3. Interaction of rotating electrically charged bodies \
4. Maxwell's equations for gravitomagnetism
5. Some properties of nucleons \
- Application \
- References \

1. Introduction

They write: "*The need to introduce the concept of strong interactions arose in the 1930s, when it became clear that neither the phenomenon of gravitational nor the phenomenon of electromagnetic interaction could answer the question of what binds nucleons in nuclei.*" Strong interactions between nucleons today are described in a very complex theory, containing many assumptions and representing an "*eclectic picture: next to mathematically rigorous calculations, semi-quantitative approaches based on quantum mechanical intuition are adjacent, which, however, perfectly describe experimental data.*"

Below, we again attempt to describe strong interactions between nucleons as a variant of gravitational interactions. The proposed theory can

be easily tested, since (as just said) there are excellently described experimental data - there will be no need for long discussions and arguments.

2. Interaction of moving electric charges

Fig. 1.

Consider fig. 1, where at points A and B are shown two charges q_1 and q_2 , moving at speeds v_1 and v_2 , respectively. It is known [2] that the magnetic induction of the field created by the charge q_2 at the point where the charge q_1 is currently located is (hereinafter we use the SI system)

$$\overline{\mathbf{B}} = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} q_2 (\overline{\mathbf{v}}_2 \times \overline{\mathbf{r}}) / r^3. \quad (1)$$

In this case, the vector $\overline{\mathbf{r}}$ is directed from the point where the moving charge q_2 is located. Lorentz force acting on charge q_1 from the side of charge q_2 ,

$$\overline{\mathbf{F}}_{12} = q_1 ((\overline{\mathbf{v}}_1 - \overline{\mathbf{v}}_2) \times \overline{\mathbf{B}}) \quad (2)$$

or

$$\overline{\mathbf{F}}_{12} = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} q_1 q_2 ((\overline{\mathbf{v}}_1 - \overline{\mathbf{v}}_2) \times (\overline{\mathbf{v}}_2 \times \overline{\mathbf{r}})) / (r^3). \quad (3)$$

Here $(\overline{\mathbf{v}}_1 - \overline{\mathbf{v}}_2)$ is the speed of movement of charge q_1 relative to charge q_2 , i.e. relative to the field with magnetic induction $\overline{\mathbf{B}}$. The projection of force (3) onto the vector $\overline{\mathbf{r}}$ is denoted as

$$\overline{F}_{12r}. \quad (5)$$

Similarly, the Lorentz force acting on the charge q_2 from the side of the charge q_1

$$\overline{F}_{21} = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} q_2 q_1 \left((\overline{v}_2 - \overline{v}_1) \times (\overline{v}_1 \times \overline{r}) \right) / (r^3). \quad (6)$$

or

$$\overline{F}_{21} = \frac{-\mu}{4\pi} q_2 q_1 \left((\overline{v}_2 - \overline{v}_1) \times (\overline{v}_1 \times \overline{r}) \right) / (r^3). \quad (7)$$

The projection of force (7) onto the vector \overline{r} is denoted as

$$\overline{F}_{21r}. \quad (7.1)$$

Obviously, the total force of attraction of charges q_1 and q_2 is equal to

$$\overline{F} = \overline{F}_{12r} - \overline{F}_{21r}. \quad (7.2)$$

or is equal to the projection onto the vector \overline{r} of the force

$$\overline{F} = 2 \frac{\mu}{4\pi} q_1 q_2 r^{-3} \left(\begin{aligned} & \left((\overline{v}_1 - \overline{v}_2) \times (\overline{v}_2 \times \overline{r}) \right) \\ & + \left((\overline{v}_2 - \overline{v}_1) \times (\overline{v}_1 \times \overline{r}) \right) \end{aligned} \right). \quad (7.3)$$

This projection is

$$\overline{F}_r = 2 \frac{\mu}{4\pi} q_2 q_1 r^{-3} \hat{f}_r, \quad (8)$$

where \hat{f}_r is the projection onto the vector \overline{r} of the force

$$\hat{f} = \left(\begin{aligned} & \left((\overline{v}_1 - \overline{v}_2) \times (\overline{v}_2 \times \overline{r}) \right) \\ & + \left((\overline{v}_2 - \overline{v}_1) \times (\overline{v}_1 \times \overline{r}) \right) \end{aligned} \right) \quad (8a)$$

or

$$\hat{f} = \left((\overline{v}_1 \times (\overline{v}_2 \times \overline{r})) + (\overline{v}_2 \times (\overline{v}_1 \times \overline{r})) \right) \quad (9)$$

It is known that the projection of the vector \hat{f}_r onto the vector \overline{r} is defined as

$$\hat{f}_r = (\hat{f} \cdot \overline{r}) / r \quad (10)$$

From (8, 10) we find:

$$\overline{F}_r = 2 \frac{\mu}{4\pi} q_2 q_1 r^{-3} \hat{f}_r. \quad (11)$$

Here we neglect mechanical forces, considering massless charges.

Here we also neglect the forces of interaction of static charges. However, the energy of this pair of electric charges is the energy of the electric field of these charges. The appearance of the second charge next to the first does not change the energy of the first and second charges. Their mutual movement cannot change their overall energy. Thus, the considered movement occurs without energy consumption. This process can be compared with the movement of an electromagnetic wave: there is movement, but the energy of the wave is conserved; there is a flow of energy, but there is no change in the energy of the wave. In our case, there is also a

movement of charges (and the associated movement of energy), but there is no change in the total energy.

3. Interaction of rotating electrically charged bodies

Let the charges q_1 and q_2 be in the bodies T_1 and T_2 , respectively, which rotate around their axis with angular velocities $\overline{\omega}_1$ and $\overline{\omega}_2$, respectively. Then the vectors of linear velocities

$$\overline{v}_1 = \overline{\omega}_1 \times \overline{a}_1, \tag{12}$$

$$\overline{v}_2 = \overline{\omega}_2 \times \overline{a}_2, \tag{13}$$

In fig. 2 shows these bodies, charges q_1 and q_2 and vectors \overline{a}_1 and \overline{a}_2 of the positions of these charges. We have:

$$\overline{a}_2 + \overline{r} - \overline{a}_1 - \overline{L} = 0 \tag{14}$$

or

$$\overline{r} = \overline{a}_1 + \overline{L} - \overline{a}_2. \tag{15}$$

Thus, it follows from (11, 12, 13) that

$$\overline{F}_r = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} q_2 q_1 \omega_2 \omega_1 \overline{F}_{ro}(\overline{a}_1, \overline{a}_2), \tag{16}$$

or

$$\overline{F}_{ro}(\overline{a}_1, \overline{a}_2) = r^{-4} (\hat{f} \cdot \overline{r}) \tag{17}$$

is the function defined by (15, 13, 12, 9) for the given \overline{L} , $\overline{\omega}_1$, $\overline{\omega}_2$.

Fig. 2.

4. Maxwell's equations for gravitomagnetism

In [3], the author proposed a new solution of Maxwell's equations for gravitomagnetism, which is used to construct mathematical models of various natural phenomena (sand vortex, sea currents, whirlpool, funnel, water soliton, water and sand tsunamis, turbulent flows, additional (non-

Newtonian) interaction forces celestial bodies). All these models use the concept of mass currents as flows of mass particles. The speed of mass particles can be very low and often their flow can be invisible as well as the flow of electrons. But the existence of these phenomena and the possibility of constructing these mathematical models, similar to mathematical models of direct current in electrodynamics [4], confirm the assumption of the existence of mass currents and the interaction of mass particles, completely analogous to the interaction of electric charges.

Based on this, it can be assumed that any movement of a body is accompanied by a mass current, similarly to how the rotation of a charged body is accompanied by a convection electric current. Eichenwald [5] showed that such a current creates magnetic induction. Based on the complete analogy between Maxwell's equations for electrodynamics and gravitomagnetism [2], it can be argued that when a body moves, gravitomagnetic induction is created. A mass m moving in a gravimagnetic field with a speed v is acted upon by the Lorentz gravitomagnetic force (analogue of the Lorentz magnetic force).

In electrodynamics, the magnetic induction B is defined through the magnetic strength H as $B = \mu H$, where μ is the absolute magnetic permeability of the medium, and for vacuum $\mu \approx 10^{-6}$.

In electrodynamics, gravitomagnetic induction B is defined through gravitomagnetic strength H as

$$B = G \xi H, \tag{18}$$

where $G \approx 10^{-11}$ is the gravitational constant, $\xi \approx 10^{12}$ is the coefficient of the gravitational permeability of the vacuum determined experimentally. For what follows, note that

$$G \xi \approx 10^7 \mu, \tag{19}$$

Thus, the formulas used above are applicable in gravitomagnetism when the coefficient μ is replaced by the coefficient $G \xi$. At the same time, we can use the entire mathematical apparatus (including designations) described above in application to electrodynamics to describe the interaction of bodies with mass, and by charges we mean elementary masses - EM.

5. Some properties of nucleons.

We use the above to describe the interaction of nucleons. In this case, we will assume that the nucleon is a ball with a uniform distribution of mass over the volume, has an angular velocity of rotation around its own axis, and this axis retains its orientation when the nucleon moves. We can apply several previous conclusions directly to nucleons. We use the above to describe the interaction of nucleons. In this case, we will assume that the

nucleon is a ball with a uniform distribution of mass over the volume, has an angular velocity of rotation around its own axis, and this axis retains its orientation when the nucleon moves. We can apply several previous conclusions directly to nucleons.

Nucleons contain many uniformly distributed EMs. By integrating functions (16, 17) over the volumes of two nucleons, one can find the function of attraction of these nucleons. If q_2, q_1 is EM, then the force of attraction of two nucleons with volumes V is determined by (16, 17) as

$$\overline{F}_V = \int_V \overline{F}_r dV = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} q_2 q_1 \omega_2 \omega_1 \int_V \overline{F}_{ro}(\overline{a}_1, \overline{a}_2) dV. \quad (21)$$

Total nucleon mass

$$Q = \int_V q dV. \quad (22)$$

If the nucleon body is divided into n^3 elements containing EM q , then

$$q = Q/n^3. \quad (23)$$

Then the force of attraction of two nucleons with volumes V is

$$\overline{F}_V = \sum_V (\overline{F}_r) = A n^{-3} \sum_V (\overline{F}_{ro}), \quad (24)$$

where

$$A = \frac{\mu}{4\pi} Q_2 Q_1 \omega_2 \omega_1. \quad (24a)$$

Further we will refer to the programs in which it is indicated:

D is the nucleon diameter,

R is the distance between nucleon centers,

δ is the gap between nucleons (along the line connecting the nucleon centers).

Wherein

$$L = D + \delta, \quad (25)$$

$$\dot{L} = [L, 0, 0]. \quad (26)$$

In the above examples, the **relative force of interaction** is indicated, namely, the ratio of this interaction force (24) to the nucleon diameter D :

$$\overline{F}_{V0} = \overline{F}_V / D. \quad (27)$$

Example 1 shows that $A=1$

$$\overline{F}_{V0} \approx e^{-5(\log D)+1}. \quad (28)$$

From (27, 28) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{F}_{V0} / A &\approx e^{-(6\log D)+5} = 10^{-\log(e|(6\log D)+5)} = i \\ i &10^{-0.43(6\log D)+5} = 10^{-(2.6\log D)+2.2}, \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

$$\overline{F}_V = A D \overline{F}_{V_0} = A D 10^{-(2.6 \log |D| + 2.2)}. \quad (30)$$

Let be

$$D = 10^{-a}. \quad (31)$$

Then

$$\overline{F}_V = A D \overline{F}_{V_0} = A \cdot 10^{[2.6a - 2.2]}. \quad (32)$$

For comparison, consider the Coulomb repulsion force of two touching nucleons:

$$\overline{F}_k = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon} \frac{q_2 q_1}{D^2/4} \approx \frac{q_2 q_1}{\pi D^2 10^{-11}} \quad (33)$$

or, taking into account (31),

$$\overline{F}_k \approx \frac{Q_2 Q_1}{\pi} 10^{2a+11}. \quad (34)$$

In this way,

$$\frac{\overline{F}_V}{\overline{F}_k} \approx \frac{A \cdot 10^{[2.6a - 2.2]}}{\frac{Q_2 Q_1}{\pi} 10^{2a+11}} = \frac{A\pi}{Q_2 Q_1} 10^{(0.6a - 13.2)}$$

or, taking into account (24),

$$\frac{\overline{F}_V}{\overline{F}_k} \approx \frac{\pi\mu\omega_2\omega_1}{4\pi} 10^{(0.6a - 13.2)} \approx \omega_2\omega_1 10^{(0.6a - 19)}. \quad (35)$$

It is known that the size of a nucleon is such that $a=15$. Then from (35) we obtain:

$$\frac{\overline{F}_V}{\overline{F}_k} \approx \omega_2\omega_1 10^{-10}. \quad (36)$$

This means that the repulsive force of two nucleons rotating with the same angular velocity ω about their own axis is **greater** than the force of the Coulomb attraction of like-charged nucleons at $\omega > 10^{-5}$.

What happens when uncharged nucleons approach each other? It can be assumed that when a proton and a neutron approach each other, the latter becomes polarized. Further, the process follows the above scenario. However, the author has not seen any reports on the possible polarization of neutrons.

Below we will consider the repulsion of uncharged nucleons as particles of mass.

Example 1 also shows that there is a certain amount of clearance

$$\delta = 3^{5D} \quad (37)$$

such that further decreasing the gap does NOT increase the force of interaction.

In **example 2**, the relations between the vectors $\omega_1, \omega_2, \dot{L}$ are sought, for which there is a contact of nucleons and the interaction force is directed strictly along the vector L. The existence of such a ratio would mean that the contact of nucleons is a stable state. It is shown that such a relationship does NOT exist! This means that in a stable position there is a gap between the nucleons. A change in this position causes such an interaction force that returns the nucleons to their previous position. In this position, of course, there is some interaction force, but movement towards this force only increases this force, which creates stability. Finding such a situation and solving other problems requires a large amount of computation and analysis. In addition, you must have access to the analysis of experimental data. The author invites to cooperation.

The product $(\delta \cdot \overline{F}_v)$ can be called the potential binding energy of two nucleons. The nucleons combine so as to minimize the potential energy of interaction. In this case, they are rotated by the forces of interaction relative to each other, without changing the orientation of the vectors ω .

It can be assumed that the configuration of the molecule is also determined by the interaction between the nucleons of the atoms, and the configuration of the crystals is determined by the interaction between the nucleons of the neighboring atoms of the adjoining molecules.

Application

Example 1. Program “yadra3.m”

In the program, $\omega_1 = [1, 0, 0]$, $\omega_2 = -\omega_1$. The horizontal in the graphs is the axis of the variable parameter “x”. With the indicated $\omega_1, \omega_2, \dot{L}$ in the force \overline{F}_v , the component directed along the vector (6) prevails. All results refer only to this component - see fig. 3.

Fig. 3.

In fig. 1, window 1 shows the natural logarithm of the function $\overline{F_{V0}}$ depending on D for $n=10, Q_1=Q_2=n^3, \delta=10^{-3D}$. Moreover, $D=10^{-x}$. This dependence can be approximated by a function of the form

$$\ln(\overline{F_{V0}}) \approx 5(x-1) = -5(\log(D)+1). \quad (30)$$

In fig. 1 in window 2 shows the natural logarithm of the function $\overline{F_{V0}}$ versus n for $Q_1=Q_2=10^3, \delta=10^{-3D}, D=10^{-7}$. Moreover, $n=5x$. It can be seen that after $n=5$ the calculation accuracy does NOT increase with increasing n . It is important to consider this when developing research programs.

In fig. 1 in window 3 shows the natural logarithm of the function $\overline{F_{V0}}$ depending on δ for $n=10, Q_1=Q_2=n^3, D=10^{-7}$. При этом $\delta=3^{-Dx}$. Moreover, $\delta=3^{-5D}$. It is seen that after $\delta=3^{-5D}$ the attractive force does NOT increase with decreasing δ .

Fig. 4

Example 2. Program “yadra4.m”

In this program, for given vectors ω_1, ω_2 and for $\delta = 0$, all possible positions of the vectors \vec{L} in spherical coordinates φ, θ are sorted out. In fig. 5, the first window shows the graph of the modulus of the vector product of

the vectors $\overline{F_{V0}}$ and \dot{L} . The fact that this vector is not equal to zero indicates that the vectors being multiplied are **not** collinear. The second window shows the modulus of the vector $\overline{F_{V0}}$.

Fig.5

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